

ISORROPIA-lite: A comprehensive atmospheric aerosol thermodynamics module for Earth System Models

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Abstract. Aerosol simulations especially for Earth System Models require a thermodynamics module with a good compromise between rigor and computational efficiency. We present and evaluate ISORROPIA-lite, an accelerated and simplified version of the widely used ISORROPIA-II v.2.3 aerosol thermodynamics model, expanded to include the effects of water uptake from organics and an updated interface communicating simulation diagnostics and information. ISORROPIA-lite assumes the aerosol is in metastable equilibrium (i.e., salts do not precipitate from supersaturated solutions) and treats the thermodynamics of $\text{Na}^+ - \text{NH}_4^+ - \text{SO}_4^{2-} - \text{NO}_3^- - \text{Cl}^- - \text{Ca}^{2+} - \text{K}^+ - \text{Mg}^{2+} - \text{Organics} - \text{H}_2\text{O}$ aerosol using binary activity coefficients from precalculated look-up tables. Off-line comparison between ISORROPIA-II and ISORROPIA-lite (without organic water effects) for more than 330,000 atmospherically-relevant states demonstrated that *i*) ISORROPIA-lite provides virtually identical results with ISORROPIA-II in metastable mode and *ii*) differences between stable mode ISORROPIA-II and ISORROPIA-lite are less than 25% for the concentrations of the various semivolatile aerosol components and similar to the differences between stable and metastable modes of ISORROPIA-II. Using ISORROPIA-lite reduced computational cost by 35% compared to ISORROPIA-II simulations in stable mode with online calculation of binary activity coefficients. Application of ISORROPIA-lite in the PMCAMx chemical transport model accelerated the 3D simulations by about 10% compared to using ISORROPIA-II in stable mode with changes in the concentrations of the major aerosol components of less than 10%. Simulations considering the effects of the organic aerosol water did not slow down ISORROPIA-lite but increased the concentrations of the inorganic semivolatile components

36 especially at nighttime. The temporal evolution shown that organic water could highly
37 contribute to the total PM_1 water mass and increase the concentrations of fine nitrate and
38 ammonium within $1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in places where the organic aerosol and RH levels are high.

39

40 Keywords: aerosol thermodynamics, metastable state, nitrate, ammonium, organic water

41

42 **1. Introduction**

43 Atmospheric particulate matter (PM) is composed of inorganic salts, organic compounds and
44 elemental carbon, oxides of trace metals, crustal material and water. Inorganic salts often
45 constitute 50% or more of fine particulate matter (particles with diameter less than $2.5 \mu\text{m}$)
46 with sulfate (SO_4^{2-}), bisulfate (HSO_4^-), ammonium (NH_4^+), nitrate (NO_3^-), chloride (Cl^-) and
47 sodium (Na^+) ions being the dominant ones (Heitzenberg, 1989; Fountoukis and Nenes,
48 2007). Additionally, the potassium cation, K^+ , often dominant in the fine aerosol mode in
49 case of biomass burning events, was used in the study of Metzger et al. (2006), who
50 investigated the importance of mineral cations and organic acids in the gas-aerosol
51 partitioning of reactive nitrogen compounds. Dust components such as Ca^{2+} , and Mg^{2+}
52 together with hygroscopic sea salt (Na^+ , Cl^-) are found mainly in the coarse PM fraction. The
53 inorganic fraction is often responsible for most of the water uptake by fine PM and therefore
54 for a large fraction of the interactions between aerosols and atmospheric radiation (Burgos et
55 al., 2019). The inorganic fraction largely controls the aerosol pH, which together with aerosol
56 water determine the sensitivity of PM to precursor emissions, chemical reaction rates (Tilgner
57 et al., 2021) and shape the many impacts aerosol has on climate, public health and ecosystem
58 productivity (Pye et al., 2020; Baker et al., 2021).

59 Computing the phase state and composition of aerosols in thermodynamic equilibrium
60 is a complex computational problem, because it involves the solution of a system of several
61 nonlinear algebraic equations or the minimization of the free energy of the gas-particle
62 system (Nenes et al., 1999). Several thermodynamic equilibrium models have been developed
63 over the last four decades, treating different sets of aerosol components and using different
64 thermodynamic and numerical approaches. Characteristic examples include EQUIL (Basset
65 and Seinfeld, 1983), SEQUILIB (Pilinis et al., 1987), SCAPE2 (Kim et al., 1993),
66 ISORROPIA (Nenes et al., 1998), EQUISOLV II (Jacobson, 1999), GFEMN (Ansari and
67 Pandis, 1999a, b), AIM2 (Wexler and Clegg, 2002), EQSAM (Metzger et al., 2002a, b),
68 UHAERO (Amundson et al., 2006), ISORROPIA-II (Fountoukis and Nenes, 2007), and
69 EQSAM4clim (Metzger et al., 2016).

70 One of most important challenges that thermodynamic models face regards the phase
71 diagram used to determine the possible species present. Typically models either allow for
72 salts to precipitate out of solution when supersaturated (“stable solution”) or allow salts to
73 remain in-solution even if supersaturated (“metastable solution”). These two treatments give
74 identical solutions when the humidity exceeds the deliquescence point of the major salts in
75 solution (typically ammonium nitrate and sulfate, i.e., around 70%), while the two solutions
76 increasingly diverge as humidity levels decrease. The metastable equilibrium solution leads
77 to higher concentrations of aerosol water compared to stable aerosol, especially at
78 intermediate humidity levels (30-70%). This in turn affects the size, lifetime (e.g., Song et al.,
79 2019) and scattering efficiency of particles (e.g., Bougiatioti et al., 2016). Observations
80 suggest that metastable states may be ubiquitous in aerosol (e.g., Rood et al., 1989; Tang et
81 al., 1995), as aerosol liquid water and semi-volatile partitioning of ammonia and nitrate is
82 consistent with metastable states down to 40% RH in many field observations (Guo et al.,
83 2015; Bougiatioti et al., 2016; Guo et al., 2018). The presence of multiple dissolved salts and
84 organic species depresses the water activity in aerosol, forming eutectic mixtures that can be
85 thermodynamically stable at much lower humidity than expected from the deliquescence
86 humidity of each of the individual components in the aerosol (Brooks et al., 2002; Bertram et
87 al., 2011; Peckhaus et al., 2012). This phenomenon, known as “mutual deliquescence”
88 (Wexler and Seinfeld, 1991), can greatly promote the presence of thermodynamically stable
89 water in aerosol down to low RH and tends to support a “metastable-like” liquid water
90 content and thermodynamic state (Brooks et al., 2003; Parsons et al., 2004).

91 Organic aerosol, although less hygroscopic than inorganic aerosol, could also
92 contribute significantly to the total aerosol water (Guo et al., 2015; Bougiatioti et al., 2016;
93 Jathar et al., 2016; Jin et al., 2020). This aerosol water due to the organics further promotes a
94 “metastable-like” aerosol state. Furthermore, the added water can induce secondary inorganic
95 aerosol formation since the additional water mass drives more of the gas phase components to
96 partition to the aerosol to satisfy equilibrium (e.g., Ansari and Pandis, 2000a). These
97 feedbacks are usually not treated in thermodynamic modules and are not considered in
98 chemical transport models.

99 While adoption of thermodynamic modules at present is standard for all regional
100 chemical transport models, they are not included in many of the Earth System Models used in
101 the IPCC or other assessments, except for Metzger et al. (2018) who recently have pointed
102 out the importance of aerosol water for climate studies. For example, EC-Earth (Hazeleger et
103 al., 2011) and ECHAM (Roeckner et al., 2003) do not simulate aerosol thermodynamics,

104 while NorESM (Bentsen et al., 2013; Iversen et al., 2013) uses a zeroth-order estimate for
105 aerosol nitrate formation (Kirkevåg et al., 2013). ESMs could benefit from the improved
106 simulation of aerosol thermodynamics, as simplified parameterizations of nitrate uptake and
107 hygroscopicity may lead to errors in simulated light scattering and associated climate forcing
108 (Burgos et al., 2020).

109 Part of the delay to adopt thermodynamic modules in ESMs is related to their
110 complex model development cycle (NRC, 2012). Computational time is another important
111 factor as thermodynamic calculations need to be repeated billions of times (or more) in such
112 frameworks and can significantly increase their computational burden. The first generations
113 of aerosol thermodynamics models paid little attention to computational efficiency, and were
114 too expensive for use in 3D frameworks. Subsequent efforts however improved solution
115 algorithms and simplified calculations so that modules were fast enough to enable their
116 integration in 3D frameworks. ISORROPIA-II (Fountoukis and Nenes, 2007) is, together
117 with EQSAM, one of the most widely used thermodynamic modules currently, largely
118 because it provides a good balance between comprehensive treatment of inorganic aerosol
119 thermodynamics and simplifications and algorithms that are computationally efficient.
120 Furthermore, ISORROPIA-II can consider the major inorganic ions present in aerosol, treat
121 both stable and metastable states and solve for two classes of problems: the gas-phase
122 equilibrium partitioning (“forward”) problem, and the equilibrium vapor pressure calculation
123 (“reverse”) problem, based on aerosol composition alone. The latter is needed when long
124 equilibration timescales demand explicit dynamic mass transfer calculations between the
125 aerosol and gas phases (Capaldo et al., 2000; Pilinis et al., 2000; Kakavas et al., 2021).

126 Despite the previous efforts to produce both accurate and computational efficient
127 aerosol thermodynamics modules, additional improvements are desired to increase their
128 suitability for the computationally demanding long simulations of ESMs. One approach is to
129 simplify the phase diagram, assuming that the aerosol is always in metastable state, especially
130 given the observational support to date. This assumption may speed up calculations at
131 intermediate RH, where the precipitation of salts out of supersaturated aerosol requires the
132 expensive solution of multiple equations. Also, at lower RH, where there is lack of an
133 aqueous phase, the simulation surface of solid aerosols is discontinuous which may cause
134 numerical instabilities in the host model. Although stable aerosol may exhibit higher
135 concentrations of aerosol ammonium and nitrate at humidity below 50% (Ansari and Pandis,
136 2000b; Moya et al., 2007; Fountoukis et al., 2009), aerosol-gas partitioning may be somewhat
137 insensitive to the actual phase state at intermittent to low RH in most of the atmosphere,

138 given that the nitrate partitioning strongly shifts to the aerosol phase at low temperatures
139 (Guo et al., 2017). This is supported by Karydis et al. (2016), who showed with the EMAC
140 global model that the tropospheric burden of nitrate aerosol decreases by just 2% when the
141 aerosol is assumed to be in a metastable state.

142 All the above suggest that simplified thermodynamic modules which assume
143 metastable aerosol may be an appropriate choice for ESMs and CTMs. Towards this, Metzger
144 et al. (2016) developed the EQSAM4clim module based on parameterizations that eliminate
145 the need for iterations. Replacing ISORROPIA with EQSAM4clim in CAMx, Koo et al.
146 (2020) reported a reduction in computational time by 4% during winter and 7% during
147 summer assuming metastable aerosols.

148 We build upon these findings and test whether assuming metastable aerosol and other
149 simplifications in ISORROPIA-II can accelerate the calculations of 3D models without
150 substantial impacts on their results. From these efforts, a new thermodynamics module,
151 ISORROPIA-lite is developed that solves only the metastable state problem and always uses
152 pre-calculated tables of binary activity coefficients to boost computational efficiency. It also
153 simulates the effects of the organic aerosol water in the partitioning of the inorganic
154 components. The predictions of ISORROPIA-lite are first compared against the predictions
155 of ISORROPIA-II in stable mode (with the complete activity coefficient module), without
156 organic aerosol water effects. Evaluations involve differences in predicted composition and
157 computational cost, and are carried out off-line and in the chemical transport model
158 PMCAMx. Then the effect of organic aerosol on the partitioning of inorganic species is
159 studied.

160

161 **2. Model description**

162 **2.1 The baseline ISORROPIA-II model**

163 ISORROPIA-II and its latest version 2.3 (Fountoukis and Nenes, 2007;
164 <http://isorropia.epfl.ch>) is the base model used a starting point for the ISORROPIA-lite
165 development. The current version contains all fixes to bugs identified in earlier versions of
166 ISORROPIA-II (see <http://isorropia.epfl.ch> and Song et al., 2018). The “baseline”
167 ISORROPIA-II model simulation used hereon explicitly calculates the activity coefficients of
168 mixtures and also assumes that the aerosol is always in a stable state, therefore it is solid at
169 RH below the mutual deliquescence RH of its components. The module is tested in the gas-
170 aerosol partitioning (“forward”) mode.

171

172 2.2 From ISORROPIA-II to ISORROPIA-lite

173 ISORROPIA-lite is based on the ISORROPIA-II (Fountoukis and Nenes, 2007) code, hence
174 it treats the thermodynamics of aerosol containing Ca^{2+} , K^+ , Mg^{2+} , SO_4^{2-} , Na^+ , NH_4^+ , NO_3^- ,
175 Cl^- , H_2O and their equilibrium with gas-phase HNO_3 , NH_3 , HCl and H_2O . A series of
176 simplifications that reduce size and increase computational efficiency have been implemented
177 in ISORROPIA-lite. The aerosol is assumed to be only in a metastable state, so all routines
178 related to the stable state solution (solid+liquid aerosol) from the original code of
179 ISORROPIA-II have been removed. The only solid salt that is allowed to form in
180 ISORROPIA-lite is calcium sulfate (CaSO_4), as it is virtually insoluble for most atmospheric
181 humidities and spontaneously precipitates out of solution. The remaining salts that can form
182 are assumed to be completely deliquesced. Further simplifications address the calculation of
183 binary activity coefficients. In ISORROPIA-II, the coefficients for specific ionic pairs (Kusik
184 and Meissner, 1978) can be computed during runtime or obtained from precalculated tables.
185 In ISORROPIA-lite, only precalculated tables are used. However, the calculation of
186 multicomponent activity coefficients is still done during runtime with the Bromley (1973)
187 method.

188 ISORROPIA-lite includes one important extension over ISORROPIA-II, in that it
189 allows organic aerosol to perturb the inorganic equilibria by contributing additional aerosol
190 water over that from the inorganic species alone. This organic aerosol water, W_o , is calculated
191 by using the κ hygroscopicity parameter (Petters and Kreidenweis, 2007) based on the
192 relative humidity and the mass of organic compounds within the inorganic aerosol phase:

$$193 \quad W_o = \frac{\rho_w}{\rho_o} \frac{C_o \kappa}{\left(\frac{1}{RH} - 1\right)}, \quad (1)$$

194 where ρ_w is the density of water and ρ_o the density, C_o the concentration and κ the
195 hygroscopicity parameter of the organic aerosol. W_o is calculated every time the
196 ISORROPIA-lite solution algorithm requests calculation of aerosol water, and is added to the
197 water computed from the other inorganic components using the Zdanovskii, Stokes, and
198 Robinson (ZSR) equation. This additional aerosol water W_o increases the total aerosol water
199 and tends to slightly elevate the aerosol pH. Both these effects in turn affect the partitioning
200 of the inorganic semi-volatile species. Organic effects on the activity coefficient of inorganic
201 species are not considered because previous work has shown that they are of secondary
202 importance – at least for aerosol pH (e.g., Battaglia et al., 2019; Pye et al., 2020).

203 ISORROPIA-lite v1.0 can be used to solve the partitioning (forward) problem. The
204 known quantities (inputs) are RH, temperature (T), the organic aerosol concentration,
205 hygroscopicity parameter κ and density and the total (gas+aerosol) concentrations of
206 ammonia, sulfuric acid, sodium, hydrochloric acid, nitric acid, calcium, potassium, and
207 magnesium. The appropriate set of equilibrium equations are solved together with
208 electroneutrality, water activity equations and mass conservation in order to compute the
209 concentrations of species at thermodynamic equilibrium. Details on the thermodynamic
210 properties of the modeled species, the equilibrium reactions and constants and the
211 thermodynamic equilibrium calculations of inorganic species can be found in Fountoukis and
212 Nenes (2007).

213

214 **2.3 PMCAMx description and application**

215 PMCAMx is the research version of the publicly available CAMx model (Environ, 2003). It
216 simulates vertical and horizontal advection, vertical and horizontal dispersion, dry and wet
217 deposition and gas, aqueous, and aerosol chemistry. The gas-phase chemical mechanism used
218 here is a modified SAPRC mechanism to account for the VBS treatment of the secondary
219 organic aerosol and it includes 237 reactions of 18 radicals and 91 gases (Carter, 2000;
220 Environ, 2003). The aerosol size and composition distribution is described using 10 size bins
221 with diameters from 40 nm to 40 μm . The model assumes that all particles in each size bin
222 have the same composition. The aerosol species simulated are primary and secondary
223 organics, elemental carbon, crustal species, sodium, chloride, sulfate, nitrate, ammonium,
224 calcium, potassium, magnesium and water. In this application of PMCAMx, we use the bulk
225 equilibrium assumption; therefore the bulk aerosol and gas phases are assumed to be always
226 in equilibrium.

227 PMCAMx was applied over Europe during May 2008, which is the EUCAARI
228 summer intensive measurement period. The modeling domain, including all of Europe, is a
229 region of $5400 \times 5832 \text{ km}^2$. The grid resolution used is $36 \times 36 \text{ km}$ (24,300 cells per layer)
230 and there are 14 vertical layers with the total height extending up to 6 km above ground level.
231 Inputs to the model such as horizontal wind components, vertical diffusivity, temperature,
232 pressure, water vapor, rainfall, and clouds are provided by the Weather Research and
233 Forecasting (WRF) meteorological model (Skamarock et al., 2008). Land emissions from the
234 GEMS dataset (Visschedijk et al., 2007) and international shipping emissions were included
235 in the anthropogenic gas-phase emissions. Anthropogenic particulate emissions include the
236 elemental and organic carbon emissions (Kulmala et al., 2009) and the urban dust emissions

237 (Kakavas and Pandis, 2021). Biogenic emissions were based on MEGAN (Guenther et al.,
238 2006). Sea-salt emissions were developed using the approach of O’Dowd et al. (2008). More
239 details about the inputs can be found in Fountoukis et al. (2011) and Kakavas and Pandis
240 (2021).

241 The results of this simulation were used for the online and off-line evaluation of
242 ISORROPIA-lite. Because the thermodynamic calculations in this application of PMCAMx
243 are performed assuming always equilibrium between PM_{10} and the gas phase, the monthly
244 average PM_{10} concentrations of each cell of each atmospheric level of PMCAMx, including
245 ground level, were used to create an input file for off-line ISORROPIA-lite and
246 ISORROPIA-II forward mode simulations. Also for this, the predicted gas concentrations of
247 nitric acid, ammonia, hydrochloric acid and sulfuric acid were added to the particulate phase
248 concentrations together with the simulated RH and temperature. The organic aerosol
249 concentrations are not included at first to focus on the differences between ISORROPIA-lite
250 and ISORROPIA-II from the assumption of aerosol state and binary activity coefficient
251 approach. This test is atmospherically-relevant because it includes atmospheric states
252 encountered over a continental scale, including terrestrial and marine environments.

253

254 **3. Results and discussion**

255 **3.1 ISORROPIA-lite off-line evaluation**

256 **3.1.1 Computational requirements**

257 ISORROPIA-lite was first evaluated off-line against ISORROPIA-II in stable mode (with
258 online binary activity coefficients calculation) for a standard set of conditions (Table 1).
259 331,520 tests were performed covering fully the corresponding chemical and meteorological
260 space. All the timing tests were performed on a computer with two Intel Xeon Silver 4110
261 CPU 2.1 GHz and 64 GB of RAM. ISORROPIA-II required 6.5 CPU s, 52% more than the
262 4.2 CPU s required by ISORROPIA-lite. Therefore, replacing ISORROPIA-II by
263 ISORROPIA-lite, for these tests at least will result in a reduction of the corresponding
264 computational cost by approximately 35%. Running ISORROPIA-lite using online
265 calculation of binary activity coefficients slowed down the calculations by 26%.

266 In the second off-line test we used the predictions of PMCAMx at ground level over
267 Europe for May 2008, a total of over 23,000 points as inputs for ISORROPIA-II in stable
268 mode and ISORROPIA-lite. These cases are studied separately because of their relevance to
269 near ground air quality and human health. For this second test ISORROPIA-II required 55%
270 more CPU time than ISORROPIA-lite (0.42 versus 0.27 s). The acceleration of the

271 calculations by ISORROPIA-lite was the same as the first test and equal to 35% of the time
272 required by ISORROPIA-II. The use of the look-up tables of the binary activity coefficients
273 reduced the CPU time by 18% of ISORROPIA-II and the simplification of the metastable
274 state contributed another 17%.

275 Differences in the frequency of occurrence of conditions suitable for the formation of
276 a stable aerosol state (solid+liquid particles) but also for the activity coefficients calculation
277 at lower temperatures are responsible for the differences in the computational performance of
278 the two thermodynamic models. The higher the frequency of such conditions the higher the
279 computational savings offered by the new module. The calculation of the organic aerosol
280 water has a negligible effect on the computational speed of ISORROPIA-lite (not shown).

281

282 3.1.2 Comparison of ISORROPIA-lite against ISORROPIA-II

283 We use as metrics for the comparison of the predictions of the various models the normalized
284 mean bias (NMB) and the normalized mean error (NME), defined as:

285

$$286 \quad NMB_j = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n [C_{i,j}^{\text{lite}} - C_{i,j}^{\text{II}}]}{\sum_{i=1}^n C_{i,j}^{\text{II}}} \quad (2)$$

287

$$288 \quad NME_j = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |C_{i,j}^{\text{lite}} - C_{i,j}^{\text{II}}|}{\sum_{i=1}^n C_{i,j}^{\text{II}}} \quad (3)$$

289

290 where $C_{i,j}^{\text{lite}}$ and $C_{i,j}^{\text{II}}$ are the corresponding concentrations of species j predicted by each
291 model for test case i and n is the total number of test cases examined.

292 The predictions of ISORROPIA-lite (without organic aerosol water) were first
293 compared with those of ISORROPIA-II in stable mode (with online calculation of binary
294 activity coefficients) model for both off-line tests. The discrepancies between the
295 ISORROPIA-lite and ISORROPIA-II predictions for the concentrations of the various
296 semivolatile aerosol components are all less than 25% (Table 2). They are lower for chloride
297 and ammonium and higher for nitrate and water. For the gas phase components, they are also
298 less than 25% (Table 2). For gas-phase ammonia and hydrochloric acid they are 10% or less
299 and for nitric acid they are less than 25%. These differences are mainly found at low to

300 intermediate RHs, when the stable mode solution contains both a solid and a liquid phase.
301 Please note that for many of these conditions, the metastable solution may reflect better the
302 ambient aerosol state; these discrepancies should therefore not be interpreted as
303 ISORROPIA-lite errors but uncertainty due to its phase state.

304 For both set of conditions (standard and European), ISORROPIA-lite tends to predict
305 higher amounts of inorganic aerosol and lower concentrations of inorganic gases than
306 ISORROPIA-II in stable mode (Fig. 1). The mean errors are small and range from 4.2% for
307 chloride, to 24% for nitrate. For water, the mean error was 42% for the standard set of
308 conditions and 14% for the European set. The highest discrepancies are found for the
309 hydrogen ion (H^+) predictions (137% for the standard set, 68% for the European ground set),
310 which translates to a pH uncertainty of approximately 0.15 units.

311 The effect of changing both the binary activity coefficient calculations and metastable
312 state assumption, on the predictions of ISORROPIA-II and the discrepancies with
313 ISORROPIA-lite is quantified one change at a time. The introduction of the pre-calculated
314 tables has a small effect on ISORROPIA-II (stable mode) predictions for both set of
315 conditions with mean errors varying from 1.2% for chloride to 6.6% for nitric acid (Table 2).
316 Even for $[H^+]$, the mean error is equal to 12% for the standard set and 9.2% for the European
317 conditions (Fig. 2). The simplification leads to slightly lower predicted concentrations with
318 biases less than 2.5% for all the major aerosol components and water, and slightly higher
319 concentrations (biases less than 4.1%) for all the inorganic gases. These results strongly
320 suggest that pre-calculated binary activity coefficient tables introduce small errors in both set
321 of conditions and represent a relatively safe way to speed up the calculations.

322 As expected, the assumption of metastable aerosol for all RH conditions has the
323 largest impact on simulated concentrations. The comparison of a version of ISORROPIA-II
324 which uses the complete activity coefficient module in stable and metastable mode was used
325 for the analysis. For both set of conditions, the normalized mean errors range from 4.1% for
326 chloride to 24% for nitric acid (Table 2). Water mean error was equal to 42% for the standard
327 set of conditions and 13% for the European ground conditions. The highest discrepancy
328 (137% for the standard set, 65% for the European set) was found for $[H^+]$ (Fig. 3). Therefore,
329 the assumed metastable equilibrium state is mainly responsible for the differences of the
330 predictions of the two thermodynamic modules and their respective configuration.

331 The upper levels of the atmosphere, included in the standard set of conditions, are
332 characterized by lower RHs and temperatures than at ground level – and with it, the
333 frequency where the metastable and stable assumptions differ. In both sets of conditions, the

334 greatest discrepancies were found in water and hydrogen ion levels because the stable state
335 solution of ISORROPIA-II at low RH predicts solid aerosol where water and $[H^+]$ do not
336 exist (and for the sake of comparison were set equal to zero), and ISORROPIA-lite always
337 predicts an aqueous solution.

338

339 **3.2 ISORROPIA-II vs. ISORROPIA-lite in PMCAMx**

340 Fig. 4 presents the predicted ground level concentrations of the major inorganic PM
341 components by PMCAMx using ISORROPIA-II in stable mode (with the complete activity
342 coefficient module) and the corresponding changes when ISORROPIA-lite (without organic
343 aerosol water effects) is used.

344 Sodium and chloride concentrations are higher over the sea, because they are the
345 major components of sea salt, and lower over continental Europe. When ISORROPIA-lite
346 was used for the simulation of aerosol thermodynamics in PMCAMx, predicted sodium and
347 chloride concentrations decreased on average by approximately 0.6%. The low maximum
348 difference of $0.2 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ over the central Mediterranean Sea occurs because metastable state
349 particles have more water, are larger and hence have a higher deposition velocity.

350 Predicted nitrate concentrations exceed $7 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ over the Netherlands, Belgium,
351 United Kingdom, and northern France, while for the rest of Europe lower concentrations are
352 predicted (up to $3 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) when ISORROPIA-II in stable mode is used. Using ISORROPIA-
353 lite caused an increase on average nitrate concentration of approximately 10%. More
354 specifically, average nitrate increased up to $0.4 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ over most of continental Europe
355 except Belgium and Netherlands, where an average decrease of $0.1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ is predicted. In
356 Belgium and Netherlands, nitrate resides mainly in the particulate phase and the RH is
357 generally high enough so that changes in liquid water content have minor impact on nitrate,
358 while in other European locations, changes have a stronger impact.

359 Ammonium levels up to $3.5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ are predicted in areas with high nitrate
360 concentrations when ISORROPIA-II in stable mode is used, existing mainly as ammonium
361 sulfate, ammonium nitrate and ammonium chloride. Ammonium increased on average by 2%
362 when we used ISORROPIA-lite. More specifically, average ammonium concentrations
363 increased up to $0.1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and decreased by $0.05 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in the same areas where nitrate did.
364 Compared to nitrate, ammonium in Belgium and the Netherlands resides mainly in the gas-
365 phase. Therefore, in such cases, changes in the liquid water content have minor impact on
366 ammonium (Nenes et al., 2020), while for the rest of Europe a stronger impact emerges.

367 Sulfate concentrations using ISORROPIA-II in stable mode are high over the
368 Mediterranean and neighboring countries such as Italy and Greece (up to $6 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$), while for
369 the rest of Europe concentrations less than $5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ are predicted. Using ISORROPIA-lite
370 caused a negligible sulfate decrease over the Mediterranean Sea of $0.02 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ and a
371 negligible increase of $0.01 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ over continental Europe.

372 Water concentrations are enhanced over the marine areas because of the higher
373 concentrations of hygroscopic sea salt, while over continental Europe are lower. As expected,
374 due to the assumed metastable state of ISORROPIA-lite for low RH values, water
375 concentrations are on average higher than for the ISORROPIA-II simulations by 6.5%. More
376 specifically, an average increase of $1\text{-}2.5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ is predicted over continental Europe, while
377 over the Mediterranean Sea higher increases are predicted (up to $7 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$). The existence of
378 high concentrations of hygroscopic sea salt together with enough RH values below the
379 deliquescence point of NaCl are responsible for the higher increases over the sea.

380 Hydrochloric acid is predicted to have higher concentrations over water especially in
381 the Mediterranean Sea (up to 0.5 ppb), while in the rest of Europe less than 0.25 ppb are
382 predicted when ISORROPIA-II in stable mode is used (Fig. 5). Sodium chloride (NaCl),
383 which concentrations are higher over the water (e.g., Mediterranean Sea), reacts with the
384 available nitric acid driving some of the existing chloride in the gas-phase. When
385 ISORROPIA-lite is used, average hydrochloric acid concentration decreased by 0.8%,
386 especially over the Mediterranean Sea and northern Italy. The average concentration
387 differences are very low (up to 0.015 ppb in Mediterranean) and occur because the additional
388 water mass, predicted by the metastable state, drove more of the gas phase to partition to the
389 aerosol to satisfy equilibrium.

390 Nitric acid concentrations are higher over the Mediterranean Sea (up to 2 ppb) than
391 the rest of Europe, where concentrations less than 1 ppb are mostly predicted (Fig. 5). Using
392 ISORROPIA-lite caused an average decrease of 2%. Average nitric acid concentrations
393 increased by 0.07 ppb over the Belgium, northern Italy and Netherlands, while in the rest of
394 Europe, decreases up to 0.07 ppb are predicted. These results are consistent with the
395 predicted PM nitrate behavior since when there is a decrease of the gas phase concentration,
396 an increase of the particulate phase is predicted and vice versa. Changes in liquid water
397 content have a minor impact on nitric acid levels.

398 Average ammonia concentrations are higher over Belgium, Netherlands, northern
399 France and northern Italy mainly because of high agricultural emissions (Fig. 5). When
400 ISORROPIA-lite is used, ammonia decreased by 2% on average. As expected, ammonia

401 increased by 0.07 ppb over Belgium and Netherlands, while in the rest of Europe decreases
402 up to 0.07 ppb are predicted.

403 The computational time needed for the entire simulation during May 2008 by
404 PMCAMx using ISORROPIA-II in stable mode and with the complete activity coefficient
405 module was 64 CPU h. Using ISORROPIA-lite for the simulation of aerosol thermodynamics
406 in PMCAMx reduced the required computational time by approximately 6 CPU h (9%
407 reduction).

408 In general, the higher levels of aerosol water associated with the metastable state drive
409 more of the semi-volatile gases to the aerosol to satisfy equilibrium. However, there are
410 places such as Belgium and the Netherlands with high enough RH values, where nitrate
411 resides mainly in the particulate and ammonium in the gas-phase, so that the changes in
412 liquid water content have a minor impact (Nenes et al., 2020). Nevertheless, the average
413 predicted concentration differences between ISORROPIA-II and ISORROPIA-lite is minor
414 for all inorganic species in the aerosol phase.

415

416 **3.3 The effects of organic water on the thermodynamic solution**

417 **3.3.1 Effects for equilibrium partitioning of PM₁₀**

418 For the calculation of the organic aerosol water in ISORROPIA-lite we assumed that
419 secondary organic aerosol (SOA) constitutes the only hygroscopic component of organic
420 aerosol, with a hygroscopicity parameter κ equal to 0.15 and density equal to 1 g cm^{-3}
421 (Cerully et al., 2015). Predictions of ISORROPIA-lite with and without the effects of organic
422 aerosol water were first evaluated off-line (Fig. 6). The differences of the concentrations of
423 the semivolatile aerosol components are on average less than 5% (Table 2). For both set of
424 conditions, the presence of organic aerosol water leads to higher amounts of inorganic aerosol
425 and lower concentrations of inorganic gases. The additional water mass of the organic aerosol
426 drives more of the gas phase to partition to the aerosol to satisfy equilibrium. The mean
427 differences are small, ranging from 1.8% for ammonium to 5.3% for nitric acid. The
428 additional organic aerosol water is on average 12% of the inorganic for the standard set of
429 conditions and 8% for the European. For hydrogen ion (H^+), the predicted concentration
430 differences correspond up to 0.05 pH units. Similar low pH differences also occur when we
431 assume that the organic water is additive and affects pH without feedbacks on inorganic
432 semivolatiles (e.g., Bougiatioti et al., 2016).

433 The predicted ground level concentrations of the major inorganic PM components by
434 PMCAMx using ISORROPIA-lite when the organic aerosol water is absent in the simulations

435 and the corresponding changes when is present are shown in Fig. 7. As expected, sulfate is
436 not affected from the presence of the additional water mass of the organic aerosol. Sodium
437 concentrations when the organic aerosol water is present in the simulation decreased on
438 average by approximately 0.2% due to the increase of the dry deposition rate. Some of the
439 chloride deposited together with sodium, but the presence of additional organic aerosol water
440 over the sea drove more of the gas phase to the aerosol. Therefore, chloride concentrations
441 increased on average by 0.3% with a maximum negligible difference of $0.02 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ over
442 southern Atlantic. Predicted nitrate concentrations increased on average by approximately
443 4%. More specifically, nitrate increased over continental Europe by $0.25 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ with highest
444 average increases over Belgium, northern France, and Netherlands. Ammonium increased on
445 average by approximately 1% when the organic aerosol water is present in the simulation
446 with average concentration increases up to $0.08 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in the same areas where nitrate did.

447 Hydrochloric acid concentrations in the presence of the additional water mass
448 decreased on average by 1.5%, especially over the sea part of Europe, where average
449 decreases of approximately 0.01 ppb are predicted (Fig. 8). Nitric acid concentrations when
450 the organic aerosol water is present in the simulation as expected decreased on average by
451 1%. Average nitric acid concentrations decreased by 0.04 ppb over the Belgium, Italy and
452 Netherlands, while in the rest of Europe small decreases up to 0.03 ppb are predicted (Fig. 8).
453 Ammonia concentrations decreased on average by 0.9%. More specifically, ammonia
454 decreased by 0.1 ppb over Belgium, northern France and Netherlands, while in the rest of
455 Europe decreases up to 0.08 ppb are predicted (Fig. 8). The results are consistent with the
456 predicted PM behavior since when there is a decrease of the gas phase concentration, an
457 increase of the particulate phase is predicted and vice versa.

458 As expected, due to the additional water mass of the organic aerosol, water
459 concentration increased on average by 8% over the modeling domain with an average
460 increase of $1\text{--}4 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ over continental Europe and $8 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ over the Atlantic sea. The
461 additional water mass is mostly in the fine fraction since it is related to secondary organic
462 aerosol water which has condensed mostly on the accumulation mode.

463

464 **3.3.2 Effects on PM₁ aerosol**

465 In this section we focus on PM₁ instead of PM₁₀ because the most important effects of
466 aerosol water due to the organic are expected in this size range. The predicted ground level
467 PM₁ concentrations by PMCAMx using ISORROPIA-lite when the organic aerosol water is
468 absent in the simulations and the corresponding changes when it is present are shown in Fig.

469 9. Fine sodium decreased over the sea on average by approximately 1% when the organic
470 aerosol water is present in the simulation, due to the size increase of particles caused by the
471 additional organic water. Fine chloride concentrations increased on average by 3% with a
472 maximum difference of only $0.005 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ over continental Europe. Predicted PM_1 nitrate
473 and ammonium concentrations increased on average by 6% and 1% respectively when the
474 organic aerosol water is present in the simulation with the same absolute concentration
475 increases of these of PM_{10} , while PM_1 sulfate decreased on average by less than 0.1% with a
476 maximum difference of only $0.005 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ over continental Europe and Atlantic ocean. The
477 additional organic aerosol water increased fine water concentrations on average by 29%.

478 Together with average changes we also focus on the temporal variation of the effects
479 on four sites (Paris, Melpitz, Cabauw, and Finokalia) with different characteristics (Table 3).
480 The PM_1 water concentrations in all sites are quite variable ranging from close to zero to
481 above $100 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ when the RH approaches 100% (Fig. 10). The presence of organic aerosol
482 water as expected increased PM_1 water concentrations in all sites. Water increases of a few
483 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ are predicted during most of the days and sites. During the high RH periods PM_1
484 water increased up to $35 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in Cabauw and Finokalia, $40 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in Melpitz and $100 \mu\text{g}$
485 m^{-3} in Paris (not shown).

486 For PM_1 nitrate, concentrations up to $10 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ are predicted in Cabauw, up to $2 \mu\text{g}$
487 m^{-3} in Finokalia, and up to $7 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in Melpitz and Paris (Fig. 11). The presence of the
488 additional water mass affected PM_1 nitrate especially in Cabauw, where increases up to 0.7
489 $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ are predicted during most of the time and up to $1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ during the last day of the
490 month. As for Cabauw, increases up to $0.7 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ occurred in Melpitz and Paris, while fine
491 nitrate in Finokalia did not change during most of the time with the exception of a couple of
492 periods during which changes of $0.1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ are predicted.

493 Fine ammonium concentrations reach values of approximately $5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in Cabauw,
494 $2.5 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in Finokalia, $4 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in Melpitz, and $3 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ in Paris during May 2008 (Fig.
495 12). When the organic water effects are considered, PM_1 ammonium concentrations increase
496 up to $0.3 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$ for Cabauw, Melpitz, and Paris, while in Finokalia, PM_1 ammonium is
497 virtually unaffected. The increases occurred at the same time the corresponding ones of fine
498 nitrate did.

499 Temporal profiles of PM_1 components during the simulation period indicated that
500 secondary organic aerosol water could contribute to the total PM_1 aerosol water content and
501 influence fine nitrate and ammonium concentrations especially at nighttime. Fine chloride
502 concentrations are not expected to change significantly with time, especially in the examined

503 sites (characterized by low chloride levels), affected by the organic aerosol water. However,
504 they could be affected in other locations – especially urban environments during biomass
505 burning periods, where organic compounds and chloride salts can constitute a considerable
506 fraction of submicron aerosol (Metzger et al., 2006; Fountoukis et al., 2009; Gunthe et al.,
507 2021).

508

509 **4. Conclusions**

510 ISORROPIA-lite, a computationally efficient aerosol equilibrium module for large-scale
511 models that treats the thermodynamics of Na^+ – NH_4^+ – SO_4^{2-} – NO_3^- – Cl^- – Ca^{2+} – K^+ – Mg^{2+} –
512 Organics– H_2O aerosol systems is developed. The new module is based on ISORROPIA-II
513 version 2.3 with extensions to include the effects of organic water uptake on inorganic
514 partitioning. To increase computational speed and reduce code size, ISORROPIA-lite
515 assumes that the aerosol is always in metastable equilibrium and precalculated tables are used
516 for the binary activity coefficients. Compared to ISORROPIA-II, ISORROPIA-lite is 35%
517 faster and accelerates PMCAMx 3D simulations by approximately 10%.

518 In terms of composition, for the partitioning (forward) problem, the discrepancies
519 between ISORROPIA-lite (without organic aerosol water) and ISORROPIA-II (stable mode)
520 predictions for the concentrations of the various semivolatile aerosol components were
521 generally low (less than 25%) in the off-line tests. In PMCAMx, the results indicated that the
522 major aerosol species concentrations agree to within 10%. Most of these differences in the
523 predictions of the two modules were found at the low to intermediate RH range. However,
524 these discrepancies should not be viewed as errors of ISORROPIA-lite, since in some cases
525 the metastable state may be more close to truth.

526 Considering organic aerosol water effects in ISORROPIA-lite simulations increased
527 the concentrations of total PM_{10} water, nitrate and ammonium and decreased the
528 corresponding gas phase of inorganic semivolatiles since the additional water mass drives
529 more of the gas phase components to partition to the aerosol to satisfy equilibrium. Temporal
530 profiles indicated that organic aerosol water could contribute to the total aerosol water
531 content and increase fine nitrate (up to $1 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) and ammonium (up to $0.3 \mu\text{g m}^{-3}$)
532 concentrations especially at nighttime in places characterized by high RH and organic aerosol
533 levels. On a domain and simulation average the changes were of the order of 30% for fine
534 water and a few percent for the major inorganic aerosol components in the simulated period.
535 The effects of the organic aerosol water in aerosol partitioning in other periods and areas will
536 be the topic of future work with ISORROPIA-lite.

537

538 **Code and data availability.** The ISORROPIA-lite v1.0 thermodynamic equilibrium code is
539 available at <https://isorro피아.epfl.ch> (last access: April 2021, Nenes, 2021). The data in the
540 study is available from the authors upon request.

541

542 **Competing interests.** The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

543

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549

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Table 1: Range of concentrations for species in the off-line analysis

	Na ⁺ (µg m ⁻³)	H ₂ SO ₄ (µg m ⁻³)	NH ₃ (µg m ⁻³)	HNO ₃ (µg m ⁻³)	HCl (µg m ⁻³)	Ca ²⁺ (µg m ⁻³)	K ⁺ (µg m ⁻³)	Mg ²⁺ (µg m ⁻³)	RH (%)	T (K)
<i>Standard set of conditions^a</i>										
Min	0.024	0.52	0.28	0.04	0.02	0.003	0.002	0.001	10.6	236
Max	5.4	10.3	13.5	9.2	8.5	0.53	0.33	0.2	96	306
<i>European conditions^b</i>										
Min	0.06	0.57	0.28	0.06	0.03	0.003	0.002	0.001	12	265
Max	5.4	7.4	13.5	9.1	8.5	0.53	0.33	0.2	96	306

^a 331,520 tests

^b 23,680 tests

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Table 2: Normalized mean biases and normalized mean errors for the off-line tests

	NH ₄ ⁺	Cl ⁻	H ⁺	NO ₃ ⁻	HNO ₃ (g)	HCl (g)	NH ₃ (g)	H ₂ O	Dry PM
ISORROPIA-lite versus ISORROPIA-II (stable mode, online act. coef.)									
<i>Standard set of conditions</i>									
NMB (%)	7.8	8.4	135	24	-22	-6.2	-11	42	4.5
NME (%)	8.2	10	137	24	22	7.5	11	42	4.7
<i>European conditions</i>									
NMB (%)	7.7	3.8	64	13	-21	-4.3	-5.5	13	3.1
NME (%)	8.2	4.2	68	13	21	4.7	5.8	13	3.2
ISORROPIA-II (stable mode, tables) versus ISORROPIA-II (stable mode, online act. coef.)									
<i>Standard set of conditions</i>									
NMB (%)	-0.2	-0.4	1.4	-0.4	0.4	0.3	0.3	-1.5	-0.1
NME (%)	1.4	1.2	12	4.4	4.2	0.9	1.9	2.3	0.8
<i>European conditions</i>									
NMB (%)	-1.6	-0.9	-3.6	-2.5	4.1	1	1.2	-2.1	-0.6
NME (%)	2.5	1.3	9.2	4.1	6.6	1.4	1.8	2.4	1
ISORROPIA-II (metastable mode, online act. coef.) versus ISORROPIA-II (stable mode, online act. coef.)									
<i>Standard set of conditions</i>									
NMB (%)	7.9	8.6	136	24	-22	-6.4	-11	42	4.5
NME (%)	8.1	9.9	137	24	22	7.3	11	42	4.6
<i>European conditions</i>									
NMB (%)	8.7	4.1	65	15	-24	-4.6	-6.2	13	3.5
NME (%)	8.7	4.1	65	15	24	4.6	6.2	13	3.5
ISORROPIA-lite (organic aerosol water presence versus absence)									
<i>Standard set of conditions</i>									
NMB (%)	1.8	3.9	6.7	2.6	-3.9	-3.3	-2.9	12	0.9
NME (%)	1.8	3.9	8.1	2.6	3.9	3.3	2.9	12	0.9
<i>European conditions</i>									
NMB (%)	2.5	2.3	7	2.3	-5.3	-2.8	-2.1	8.2	1
NME (%)	2.5	2.3	8.5	2.3	5.3	2.8	2.1	8.2	1

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Table 3: Characteristics of the four selected sites

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Site	Type of site	SOA levels	Ammonium levels	Nitrate levels	Sulfate levels	RH levels	Location in Europe
Finokalia, Greece	Remote	High	Modest	Low	High	High	South
Cabauw, Netherlands	Rural	High	High	High	High	High	North
Melpitz, Germany	Rural	High	Modest	High	High	High	North
Paris, France	Urban	High	Modest	High	High	High	West

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822 **Figure 1.** Comparison of the particulate and gas-phase concentrations predicted by
 823 ISORROPIA-II in stable mode (with online binary activity coefficients calculation) and
 824 ISORROPIA-lite for the off-line simulations for the standard (black) and European (red) set
 825 of conditions: **a)** ammonium, **b)** nitrate, **c)** chloride, **d)** dry PM, **e)** water, **f)** hydrogen ion, **g)**
 826 hydrochloric acid, **h)** nitric acid, and **i)** ammonia. There are 331,520 points in these graphs.

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829 **Figure 2.** Comparison of the particulate and gas-phase concentrations predicted by
 830 ISORROPIA-II in stable mode with online binary activity coefficients calculation and with
 831 pre-calculated tables for the off-line simulations for the standard (black) and European (red)
 832 set of conditions: **a)** ammonium, **b)** nitrate, **c)** chloride, **d)** dry PM, **e)** water, **f)** hydrogen ion,
 833 **g)** hydrochloric acid, **h)** nitric acid, and **i)** ammonia. There are 331,520 points in these graphs.

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836 **Figure 3.** Comparison of the particulate and gas-phase concentrations predicted by
 837 ISORROPIA-II (with online binary activity coefficients calculation) in stable and metastable
 838 mode for the off-line simulations for the standard (black) and European (red) set of
 839 conditions: **a)** ammonium, **b)** nitrate, **c)** chloride, **d)** dry PM, **e)** water, **f)** hydrogen ion, **g)**
 840 hydrochloric acid, **h)** nitric acid, and **i)** ammonia. There are 331,520 points in these graphs.

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843 **Figure 4.** Average ground-level PM₁₀ concentrations (in $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) of **a)** sodium, **b)** chloride, **c)**
 844 nitrate, **d)** ammonium, **e)** sulfate, and **f)** water using ISORROPIA-II in stable mode with
 845 online calculation of binary activity coefficients and ISORROPIA-lite without organic water
 846 during May 2008.

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851 **Figure 5.** Average predicted ground-level concentrations (in ppb) of **a)** hydrochloric acid, **b)**
852 nitric acid and **c)** ammonia using ISORROPIA-II in stable mode with online calculation of
853 binary activity coefficients and ISORROPIA-lite without organic water during May 2008.

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865 **Figure 6.** Comparison of the particulate and gas-phase concentrations predicted by
 866 ISORROPIA-lite when the organic aerosol water is present and absent for the off-line
 867 simulations for the standard (black) and European (red) set of conditions: **a)** ammonium, **b)**
 868 nitrate, **c)** chloride, **d)** dry PM, **e)** water, **f)** hydrogen ion, **g)** hydrochloric acid, **h)** nitric acid,
 869 and **i)** ammonia. There are 331,520 points in these graphs.

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872 **Figure 7.** Average ground-level PM₁₀ concentrations (in $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) of **a)** sodium, **b)** chloride, **c)**
 873 nitrate, **d)** ammonium, **e)** sulfate, and **f)** water using ISORROPIA-lite when the organic
 874 aerosol water is absent and present in the simulation during May 2008.

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879 **Figure 8.** Average predicted ground-level concentrations (in ppb) of **a)** hydrochloric acid, **b)**
880 nitric acid and **c)** ammonia using ISORROPIA-lite when the organic aerosol water is absent
881 and present in the simulation during May 2008.

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893 **Figure 9.** Average ground-level PM₁ concentrations (in $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) of **a)** sodium, **b)** chloride, **c)**
 894 nitrate, **d)** ammonium, **e)** sulfate, and **f)** water using ISORROPIA-lite when the organic
 895 aerosol water is absent and present in the simulation during May 2008.

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898 **Figure 10.** PM₁ water concentration (in µg m⁻³) when the organic aerosol water is absent
 899 (black) and the corresponding concentration difference when is present (red) in the simulation
 900 for **a)** Cabauw, Netherlands; **b)** Finokalia, Greece; **c)** Melpitz, Germany; and **d)** Paris, France
 901 during May 2008.

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917 **Figure 11.** PM₁ nitrate concentration (in $\mu\text{g m}^{-3}$) when the organic aerosol water is absent
 918 (black) and the corresponding concentration difference when is present (red) in the simulation
 919 for **a)** Cabauw, Netherlands; **b)** Finokalia, Greece; **c)** Melpitz, Germany; and **d)** Paris, France
 920 during May 2008.

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936 **Figure 12.** PM_1 ammonium concentration (in $\mu g m^{-3}$) when the organic aerosol water is
 937 absent (black) and the corresponding concentration difference when is present (red) in the
 938 simulation for **a)** Cabauw, Netherlands; **b)** Finokalia, Greece; **c)** Melpitz, Germany; and **d)**
 939 Paris, France during May 2008.